

8T – Abelian versus Non-Abelian

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main features of the 8T it is possible to classify nature according to abelian groups and non-abelian groups. In particular it is possible to classify fermions to form an abelian group while Bosons to form non-abelian, as the author showed in the proof to the Riemann hypothesis.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Since we have proven that the arbitrary variation term contain only two distinct element which vary to one another to form a group, and nine combination of two distinct elements, we can consider matter to abelian theories. Such is in fact the case as the number of combinations from the omega minus to the proton and neutron is finite. The two elements and their joint product which is the omega minus.

$\chi: Top \rightarrow Set$

$$T = [\delta g_1, \delta g_2, \delta g_1 \times \delta g_2]$$

Matter formations than is described by abelian group theory and a finite set of transformation on finite number of elements. In contrast to theories which tries to predict how those arbitrary variations vary such as string theory, the arbitrary variations of the terms in the set is to the other element, slight variations of each term, **from itself to itself do not generate a new particle**, or else the number of combinations would be immensely bigger and that is not the case. Theories of that kind are destined to fail, as if one correlates each slight variation to a new particle you are heading to infinite amount of particles and no laws of nature of any sort.

$$\delta g_1' \leftrightarrow \delta g_1$$

The condition of stationarity imposes a restriction, any variation of the term must be accompanied with the inverse variation on the second element in the set, so that the total series would vanish into zero. In other words, the stationarity demand (1.48) is responsible for the finite number of Fermions, and the fact that they form an Abelian group. The same does not apply to Bosons. We have used the proof of the Riemann hypothesis to demonstrate they form a non-abelian group, that is evident as the primes are infinite in kind, and each Boson is prime isomorphic. As an example of the non-Abelian features of the Bosons we created an higher Bosons as a combination of odd number of lower magnitude primes:

$$N_{V_4} = 91 + 7 + 3$$

The second composition is an example:

$$N_{V_4} = 31 + 67 + 3$$

There are several unique compositions for distinct higher primes, which indicate that it is impossible to correlate higher Bosons to a constant structure that is in fact a major feature of gravity in the 8T, and the reason we consider it to be a time variant interaction. The non-Abelian feature of Bosonic particles indicate that is homomorphic, and there is a loss of information. Just as nature creates discrete amount of curvature on a continuous smooth setting, it also has features both Abelian and non-Abelian according to each spin classification. Bosons are non-Abelian, violations of stationarity and Fermions are vanishing curvature spikes, forming an Abelian group of two distinct elements and their product. The beauty is that we can reason for the Bosonic non-Abelian trait and do it with ease as we understand now given by the primordial how to represent them. That is only because 8T started with the ideas and theorems, derived the series and reasoned the aspiring infinity terms. If we just kept measuring magnitudes or kept searching for new particles, while adding new Bosons to the standard model, we would not be able to reason for their non-abelian nature. The key point is that there exist a time in science in which ideas exceed measurements, as measurements can not explain to us **why things are the way they are**. If a race has a very strong technical abilities, which manifested in highly sensitive measuring equipment, it is able to detect all the first fifty interactions, but does not know where does numbers are coming from or how many of those numbers exist, how much does it know about nature ? How much effort they invested in measurements versus a race who only needs a mathematical series and a calculator?

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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